

Digital transformation through the lens of COVID-19: The effect of a pandemic on the banking industry.

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ABSTRACT

One of the biggest drawbacks of the current pandemic is the inability to condone business in a face-to-face matter. With employees having to work from a remote location, customers having to use services from their own home or mobile devices problems will arise. The objective of this research is to understand how companies in the Financial & Insurance sector have dealt with the COVID-19 pandemic, in specific finding knowledge the sector needs in order to move forward during the pandemic and the post-COVID-19 era. To achieve the relevant knowledge and insights the research will look at the problem from three different angles, namely: IT Governance, Business Process Integration and Cybersecurity Risk Management. The research shows that effect on ITG within banking will be quite minimal in the short run but be more heavily impacted in the longer run. Further, if working from home should become a new norm, the banking industry has to keep on actively rethinking and reinventing its processes as well as services. Lastly, banking business has changed. The new ways of conducting business have given cyber criminals new opportunities, to exploit the chaos that was caused by the pandemic. Appropriate risk mitigation and prevention are deemed necessary.

Keywords

Information Management, Banking, COVID-19, IT Governance, Cybersecurity, Risk Management, Business Process Integration.

INTRODUCTION & BACKGROUND

Ever since the global spread of the COVID-19 virus a shift has taken place in the way people live their lives, do their work and how society functions. Many different sectors in our society have taken a significant hit and are still struggling under the ever presence of the current coronavirus. One of these

sectors is the Finance & Insurance sector, a sector which is one of the cornerstones of the existence of our current economy and vital in the possibility of the day to day functioning of our society. According to the report of Deloitte (Deloitte, 2020) on the catalyzation of COVID-19 on the financial services sector there are four fundamental shifts. Firstly, there is the forced adoption of online, mobile and call center channels which has led to an increase in online banking usage by customers of 35% (Crosman, 2020). Secondly, there has been an acceleration toward digital and contactless payments, for example Visa saw more than 13 million customers in latin America make their first-ever online transaction in the March quarter of this year. As third there has been an overnight virtualization of workforce and ways of working. Employees of banks were forced to work from home, with banks opting for solutions such as VPN's to help with the security of data exchanges. Finally, there has been an evolution of underlying market structure and economics.

Problem statement

One of the biggest drawbacks of the current pandemic is the inability to condone business in a face-to-face matter. With employees having to work from a remote location, customers having to use services from their own home or mobile devices a main problem arises. This is the problem of authentication - also known as the proof of identity. Before the pandemic the verification of a person could be easily done by physical means. Therefore, the effect on authentication related activities within banking due to COVID-19 will be the focus of this research. The ability to prove the identity of employees and the proof of identity to stakeholders in the absence of physical contact will be of great importance. This will have significant implications on cybersecurity and mitigating threats, as well as on authentication processes itself.

METHOD & APPROACH

The objective of this research is to understand how companies in the Financial & Insurance sector have dealt with the COVID-19 pandemic, in specific finding knowledge the sector needs in order to move forward during the pandemic and the post-COVID-19 era. Before the pandemic the problem of authentication was less urgent due to the fact the many interactions within the banking sector were done in person. With the recent shift to working from home and using services from home there has been a gap in knowledge on how banks try to operate in this changing environment. In order to gain this insight, the following research question has been formulated: ‘How has the shift in the way business is condoned and services are consumed changed the banking industry with regard to the authentication of employees and users?’

To achieve the relevant knowledge and insights the research will look at the problem from three different angles, namely: IT Governance, Business Process Integration and Cybersecurity Risk Management. From the IT Governance perspective this research analyses the change in governance for banks, Cybersecurity dives in deeper into the banks and specifically looks for risks regarding authentication of employees and users. Finally, the Business Process Integration perspective analyzes a single process. The focus of the research is the banking industry with a deeper scope on authentication. Resources required for the gathering of the knowledge will be in the form of research papers, publications by companies in the industry, news articles and journals. The objective is to show a difference in processes, governance and risk management pre-COVID-19 and the situation during the pandemic.

ANALYSIS & RESULTS

The findings of the research are discussed and split between the effects on IT Governance, Cybersecurity and Business Processes all within the scope of banking.

The effects on IT Governance

IT Governance or ITG can be defined as the processes that ensure effective and efficient use of IT within organizations as to enable achievement of its goals (Gartner, n.d.). It is not a committee nor a specially created body. ITG concerns itself with key decisions regarding IT that might have either a positive or negative effect on a corporation (Lindros, 2017). Which implies the necessity of alignment between IT strategy and business strategy.

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Therefore, the manner in which a bank handles its ITG is of detrimental value for its existence and will become even more so in the future (Ferguson, n.d.). That being said, how do banking firms govern IT? Specifically, what effect does a pandemic like COVID-19 have on ITG within the banking sector. To examine this the IT Governance matrix from Weill & Ross (figure 1) is used to shed light on how banks handled ITG before the outbreak and how it is going to evolve in the aftermath of what has recently been coined ‘the new normal’. The matrix juxtaposes the five main decision areas of IT against the governmental archetypes. The roles of these archetypes are split between input and decision (Weill & Ross, 2005). See figure 1 at the right-hand side of the page.

GOVERNANCE ARCHETYPE	DECISION DOMAIN				
	IT Principles	IT Architecture	IT Infrastructure Strategies	Business Application Needs	IT Investment
Business Monarchy	✗				✗
IT Monarchy		✗	✗		
Federal				✗	
IT Duopoly					
Feudal					

Figure 1, IT Governance Matrix

First, the ITG situation pre-COVID-19 - which is specified here as the period before March 2020 - can be found in appendix I. Prominent employees in the banking sector firmly believe that banks have become tech companies with a banking license (ING, 2017). While this statement might be deemed inappropriate or false by others, there is a degree of truth to the matter. The three largest consumer banks in the Netherlands¹ do not even differentiate between the COO and the CIO or CDTO² anymore. In terms of organizational structures, banking firms in the Netherlands have been shifting from conventional hierarchical ones towards multidisciplinary matrix structures with a higher focus on combining staff from the business and IT as to speed up time to market of products and services (Rutten, 2019). This implies that the banking industry believes that decision-making with regards to IT budget and application needs must be with the business. IT on the other hand must decide upon IT matters, that being IT Infrastructure and IT Infrastructure Strategy. IT Governance has evolved

from monarchy-based decision making to a balanced mixture of IT and business team driven decision making. Which is reflected by the matrix in appendix I. One of the most important reasons for this evolution with regards to IT Governance is of course, the technological changes of the past decades and the reliance on said technology (Tamm, Seddon, Parkes, & Kurnia, 2014). IT has become crucial for banks to be able to create, implement and deliver new services and products but at the same time IT has become a source of significant risks (Härle, Havas, Kremer, Rona, & Samandari, 2015).

Second, the situation post-COVID-19 – which means from March 2020 and onwards – will be analyzed. For good measure, a matrix is comprised to see the reaction of banks in terms of IT governance right after the outbreak. See appendix II. One should expect centralization of decision-making in times of imminent threat, especially in banks as these institutions act as gatekeepers for the assets and significant amounts of data from their customers and stakeholders. Banks are detrimental to the global economy. Which means banks had been in need of immediate enterprise-wide response due to the effect on compliance, the economy and continuity of the organization (Vantrappen & Wirtz, 2017). Thus, raising the question how IT Governance should be handled in the new normal. This last situation can be found under appendix III. It seems logical that the effects on IT Governance will be quite minimalistic at first, seeing as the current banking system will remain of great importance to the economy. In the short run, banks will enjoy a revitalization as the opportunity to lend to customers will open more during the crisis. Banks also enjoy the protection of the safety nets and access to deposit financing provided by most governments (Segal & Gerstel, 2020). Nevertheless, COVID-19 will likely accelerate further digitalization causing the sector to be in need of restructuring. This implies that - over the longer run – IT Governance in banking firms and a banks position in general might be subjected to change more heavily. BigTech and Fintech companies will become a larger threat to the sector, having the ingredients to get ahead in the post COVID-19 era (Carletti, Claessens, Fatás, & Vives, 2020). With even more stress on digitalization and looming threats in the shape of increased competition, banking firms will most likely opt for an even more decentralized way of deciding upon IT matters. This enables Business Units and multidisciplinary teams to make optimal use of their IT resources. It will also increase the effectiveness of negating external threats and shorten the reaction time to take advantage of opportunities by means of increased agility (Janssen & van der Voort, 2020).

Lastly and on a more general note, in light of the recent events, banks would do well to strive towards a more agile and adaptive manner of governing and should:

- Update the governmental framework accordingly;
- attract and retain teams with the right skillsets;
- embed risk control teams and controls within core activities and development processes;
- strengthen general resiliency;
- adopt more advanced data intelligence and architectures (Doe, Gennarini, & Zats, 2020).

The effects on authentication and related activities for the process of mortgage granting.

Company's resilience and adaptability to change is being challenged in the face of disruptive events, such as the global pandemic of COVID-19. Practically overnight, companies were forced to involuntarily participate in the digital transformation as most of the workforce had to start working remotely from home. This dramatic change of events had an impact on processes not only in the banking industry.

The objective of this part of the report is to describe how processes in the banking industry changed under the lights of the ongoing pandemic of COVID-19 with regard to Digital Transformation. In order to be able to depict the change in processes in sufficient detail, our research focuses on how the process of authentication in the case of mortgage services and connected daily routine have changed. Further, we will describe which new opportunities arose, which risks should be avoided and set a framework for the future.

The COVID-19 pandemic has challenged the banking industry in many different ways. The most visible one is the closing of bank branches. (EY, 2020) Banks had to adapt and many services were transformed and adjusted to online settings. In theory, the majority of banking services and processes are already fully digitalized and the need for banks to meet their clients in person is further declining. Before COVID-19 pandemic, banks already kept data about their clients such as financial history and shared these details with other institutions. In order to describe how processes and procedures changed, an example of authentication of documents for mortgage will be described and discussed. A mortgage is an example of a rigid banking product which occurs less frequently, requires input of sensitive documents from the client and involves active interaction with the client. For this and other reasons, it is difficult to be performed

fully digitally. Furthermore, mortgages are highly risk, customer-oriented products, which are highly regulated by national banks and other authorities.

The first diagram (see appendix IV) describes the flow of documents required by a bank for a mortgage application process, to acceptance of the mortgage offer by the client. In this process, the client is actively involved in the entire process (back and forth confirmation of proposals and correction of handed documents).

Pandemic of COVID-19 has facilitated a digital transformation in the banking industry. It can be expected that with the rising number of users of internet banking, the demand for arrangement of more sophisticated banking products will arise. Technologies, such as digital signature of documents, authorization of digital documents, digital authentication of actors (e-ID) can enable both to switch these types of products into online settings as well as to simplify the process for the client. Even though digital tools may enable to simplify the process of mortgage application for the client, from the bank perspective it seems difficult to adjust this rigid process. Second diagram depicts the process of mortgage application adjusted due to the COVID-19 pandemic circumstances. See appendix IV and V for the diagrams.

The process of mortgage application has transformed in the following ways:

- Changes in the processes due to regulation;
- extra document concerning the financial health plan is required if request is submitted by an applicant with unstable work-contract (e.g. entrepreneur, flex worker, employee with temporary contract, out-sourced worker);
- changes in the processes due to adoption of new technology;
- digital signature is allowed (before COVID-19 restricted).

Other changes:

- Processing time became longer;
- validity time for documents has decreased (from 3 to 2 months).

The opportunities for the banking sector lie in the further adoption of digital tools such as chatbots, to enable dialog with clients. Besides fully digitalized banking, COVID-19 has pointed out a new range of products such as financing opportunities for SMEs. (Conlon, 2020) It can be expected that these new opportunities as well as the change of legislation will attract new tech-savvy financial services providers and other parties to this market. Some examples can be virtual cards offered

by Revolut or Apple. (Dillet, 2018) (Girling, 2020).

Deloitte summarized three challenges for the baking industry, catalyzed by COVID-19:

- Differentiation of online products and services;
- digitalization of key processes in the value chain;
- cyber & compliance risks. (Deloitte, 2020)

The effect on authentication in terms of cyber security and risk management.

The banking sector is a highly regulated sector and a sector with immense responsibilities for the economic and social order within countries. Furthermore, the banking sector is used by virtually everybody which makes it interesting as a subject for the research. In our research we will perform a risk assessment on the banking sectors online banking, with special focus on the personal online banking tools which are in use by the public and the banks. The main area in Cybersecurity which we are focusing on is authentication. Our definition of authentication is: "Authentication is the process of identifying users and validating who they claim to be. One of the most common and obvious factors to authenticate identity is a password. If the username matches the password credential, it means the identity is valid, and the system grants access to the user." (Kedrosky, Marketing & Kedrosky, 2020). In the recent weeks and months, a surge in cyber-crime has been recorded (Lallie et al. 2020), which was possible due to the fact that many people were forced to do their banking matters from home in an unsafe environment. An increase in phishing attempts has been noted as well as fake versions of banking websites have been created in order to mislead people in order to steal their identification information.

In the field of Cybersecurity, the main focus is to protect cyber-systems against cyber-threats (Refsdal, 2015). In contrast to many of the risks which can occur in the physical world these cyber-threats are threats that exploit a cyberspace. During the COVID-19 pandemic the use of online alternatives for doing business had to be considered, since most of the world was in lockdown. This change from the face-to-face life towards digital society brought many opportunities as well as the possibility of cybercrime to rise in popularity. This also was the case for the banking industry, relying heavily on the ability of their customers to continue using their services, for example access to their bank accounts. The use of online banking was already in place well before COVID-19 broke out so the banks could continue their operations. Though many of their customers hadn't yet transferred to the world of online banking and the pandemic forced them to

do so. This created the situation where an influx of new online bank users with little to no experience with cyber threats started to do their banking online. Besides the increased risks for the customers of the banks another difficult aspect of the COVID-19 pandemic is the forced remote working that has taken over offices. Where normally an approval for large bank transfers could be obtained simply by walking into the manager’s office and asking, nowadays a digital transmission of the documents and the approval has to be done in order to get the full authorization for the transfer. This new way of working has also brought up several risks in the remote office regarding the authenticity of employees using applications for work.

When making a risk assessment several steps should be taken in order to end with a fully encompassing and usable risk assessment. These steps are Context Establishment, Risk Identification, Risk Analysis, Risk Evaluation and Risk Treatment. In this part of the paper the focus is on the risk identification, analysis, evaluation and eventually the controls which are the means of the risk treatment. For illustrative purposes figure 1 has been provided to give insights in the way the risk will be measured in this paper. The rows represent the likelihood of the risk occurring, the columns represent the impact the particular risk would have once it has occurred. Depending on the risk appetite of particular banks the threshold for when a risk is to high conclusions in the end can differ. In this paper we have set the risk appetite to be < 5. Risks above the threshold of 5 will need controls to reduce the risk, risks below the threshold could have controls set in place but this is not a necessity.

High	3,0	9	6	3
Medium	2,0	6	4	2
Low	1,0	3	2	1
		High	Medium	Low

Table 1, identification of the risk score

An important aspect of the risk management of risks in companies is the assessment of what these risks are, followed by possible controls which could mitigate either the likelihood of the risk occurring or the impact of the consequences of the risk. The controls, also known as control measures, can be of one of three possible categories (Refsdal et al. 2015). Firstly, there are control measures focused on preventing the risk to occur. Intuitively named preventative measures make risks (nearly) impossible to occur. Secondly, detective measures are tasked with making sure risks do not go unnoticed. Finally, the last type of control measures are the corrective measures which are aimed at an appropriate reaction in case of a risk which has occurred. In theory the control measures should lead

to a reduction in the impact and/or the likelihood of the risk occurring. In this paper a reduction in the impact or likelihood is measured in the same way as the initial determination of the impact or likelihood of the risk occurring. To display the possible controls to mitigate the likelihood and impact of risk the treatment identification table from Refsdal et al. is used.

Since the forced shift towards the digital platform for interacting with banking services & the shift in working from home, numerous risks have appeared. Some of the most significant ones will be discussed shortly. A huge increase in the amount of phishing attacks have been reported. In 31 out of the 38 reported cyber-attack cases in the UK some form of phishing was used in order to obtain relevant personal information (Lallie, 2020). The widespread occurrence of phishing attacks makes them a big risk for banks, mainly due to the new demographic of inexperienced internet users. When the phishing attacks succeed in their goals of retrieving relevant banking information from their victim has an impact on their financial situation as well as the image of the bank after multiple occurrences.

The same demography is susceptible to fake websites. In the UK alone there were 292 websites that were asked to be (Hill, 2020) removed, in the first three months of covid. These sites pretended to be either a bank, a government body or a random store. The visitors would be asked for their credentials, which would allow for these people to be exploited by hackers. The impact is the same as with phishing. A vulnerability found during the move to work-from-home, was social engineering hacks. Hackers contact people within firms, acting like they are someone else. This could differentiate from being someone who has a certain position in the firm like for example the CIO, but the hackers could also claim to be a customer of the bank. They try to authenticate themselves, by using different ways of deception. In America alone there were reports of over 320,000 social engineering hack attempts in 2020 up until May. In the entire year of 2019, the confirmed cases amounted to 400,000 (Shivers, 2020). Depending on who was hacked, the impact would be different. These hacks could lead to a data breach of company data and also customer data. Obviously, it could lead to image risks and to financial risks for banks and their customers too.

Risk	Likelihood	Impact	Risk amount
1. Increased amount of phishing attempts on (new) online customers, while e-banking	H	M	6
2. Mis Authentication of managers which need to authorize large bank transfers in work from home offices.	M	M	4
3. Fake banking websites / online portals	M	M	4
4. High rise in social engineering cyber attacks	M	H	6
5. Increase in usage of own devices (BYOD) with not fully secured applications (BYOD case).	L	M	2
6. Videoconferencing Risks, a not fully secured video conferencing application which could be eavesdropped on.	M	H	6

Table 4, Risk matrix pre-controls

Because it is unreasonable to expect a complete shutdown of cyber-attacks, the banks should aim for a 5 or lower on the Risk Assessment Matrix. This would be done by protecting the key areas/people. The internal security can somewhat be guaranteed. Therefore, banking firms must keep their hardware up to date, with the newest security systems. Apply two step authentication and force the use of company equipment, even when working at home. The employees need to stay educated about potential cyber security threats in their respective departments. In terms of external security, banking firms should also try to reach as many customers as possible, in order to teach them about hacks, the damage that can be done with it and how to prevent it from happening. In the tables underneath you can see 2 of the controls explained treatment identification table, the other 4 tables related to the controls are to be found under appendix VI.

Element	Treatment
Risk no	1
Incident	Increase in successful phishing attempts
Asset	Bank account of the customer
Threat source	Cyber-criminal
Threat	Gathering of personal login information for personal banking
Attack point	Customer email or phone
Vulnerability	Inadequate knowledge about the existence of phishers and how to react
Treatment / control	Open education of the customers (especially the new online customers) of the banks on how to identify and deal with phishing attempts

Table 2, treatment identification table for risk no. 1

Element	Treatment
Risk no	2
Incident	Intruder authorized bank transfers via the account of the manager
Asset	Bank funds
Threat source	Cyber-criminal
Threat	Login credentials and additional authentication methods are obtained by cyber-criminal
Attack point	Login system
Vulnerability	Unawareness of the managers about the safety requirements for their login credential
Treatment / control	Incorporating multiple authentication methods, multi factor authentication (Wang et al 2020)

Table 3, treatment identification table for risk no. 2

With proper education of both customers and employees the risks were able to get significantly decreased, in order to comply with the risk appetite of a financial firm. This is visible in the risk matrix post-control measures listed in table 5 below.

Risk	Likelihood after control	Impact after control	
1. Increased amount of phishing attempts on (new) online customers, while e-banking	L	M	2
2. Mis authentication of managers which need to authorize large bank transfers in work from home offices.	L	M	2
3. Fake banking websites / online portals	L	M	2
4. High rise in social engineering cyber attacks	L	H	3
5. Increase in usage of own devices (BYOD) with not fully secured applications (BYOD case).	L	L	1
6. Videoconferencing Risks, a not fully secured video conferencing application which could be eavesdropped on.	L	H	3

Table 5, the risk post-control measures

DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION

Discussion

It must be clear that the ITG matrix from Weill & Ross differs from company to company, yet applicability of the matrix by means of industry standards should be somewhat representative to most of the banks in modern society. The mortgage granting process is not necessarily applicable to all banks, the information with regards to the process was made available through one company and that company alone. Next, the risks and mitigation of the risks are theoretically based and will not do so well in real-life situations, for that an intensive study aimed at multiple banks and their consumers should be considered. Furthermore, most of the information for this research was gathered through articles and reports aimed at the banking industry in western countries. Therefore, the applicability of the impact on the ITG of banks all around the world might be limited. Yet the segment comes with interesting points with regards to the general effect of a pandemic on to high-leveled governmental IT aspects. As for future research, it would be interesting to know to what extent the banking sector is affected by changing business models due to a disruptive event like COVID-19. For a deep dive

with regards to the effects of the processes and risks it is advisable to start with intensive interviewing and advanced techniques to evaluate these factors in line with the impact of COVID-19.

Conclusion

Banks are being coined as IT firms with a banking license. These organizations have already taken significant measures towards decentralization of IT Decision making and governance. Therefore, the impact on ITG in the short run would be minimal. In the longer run, due to further digitization and increasing threats, the manner in which banks do business might change more severely having a greater impact on ITG and governance as a whole. Clearly COVID-19 had strong implications for the way firms operate, their daily business processes were shaken up significantly. These new ways of conducting business have given cyber criminals new opportunities, to exploit the chaos that was caused by the pandemic. Because rules were enforced onto companies by the government, firms did not have the time to properly assess risks and were forced to move quickly. This caused cyber criminals to recognize a vulnerability in banking firms and their customers, since the rates at which cyber criminals were attacking banks and customers, went through the roof. But in the end the risks were reasonably solvable. If working from home should become a new norm, the banking industry has to keep on actively rethinking and reinventing it's processes as well as services in order to be able to provide its customers the same customer experience and comfort as they were used to before the pandemic.

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APPENDIX I. IT GOVERNANCE MATRIX PRE COVID-19

		Decision Domain									
		IT Principles		IT Architecture		IT Infrastructure Strategies		Business Application Needs		IT Investment	
		Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision
Governance Archetype	Business Monarchy		■								■
	IT Monarchy				■		■				
	Feudal								■	■	
	Federal	■		■		■		■	■	■	■
	Duopoly		■	■					■		

Most common patterns for all firms

APPENDIX II. IT GOVERNANCE MATRIX AFTER COVID-19 OUTBREAK

		Decision Domain									
		IT Principles		IT Architecture		IT Infrastructure Strategies		Business Application Needs		IT Investment	
		Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision
Governance Archetype	Business Monarchy		■		■		■		■		■
	IT Monarchy			■	■	■	■				
	Feudal										
	Federal	■		■		■		■	■	■	■
	Duopoly		■	■					■		

Most common patterns for all firms

APPENDIX III. IT GOVERNANCE POST-COVID-19.

		Decision Domain											
		IT Principles		IT Architecture		IT Infrastructure Strategies		Business Application Needs		IT Investment			
		Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision		
Governance Archetype	Business Monarchy												
	IT Monarchy												
	Feudal												
	Federal												
	Duopoly												

Most common patterns for all firms

APPENDIX IV, MORTGAGE GRANTING PRE-COVID19

Title

APPENDIX V, MORTGAGE GRANTING POST-COVID19

**APPENDIX VI, TREATMENT IDENTIFICATION TABLE
FOR RISK NO. 3,4, 5 AND 6.**

<i>Element</i>	<i>Treatment</i>
Risk no	3
Incident	Increase in fake websites and online portals
Asset	Credentials of the customer
Threat source	Cyber-criminal & Malware
Threat	Gathering of personal login information & Interception of the transmission data
Attack point	Customer email or online searching activities
Vulnerability	Inadequate knowledge about the existence of phishers and how to react
Treatment / control	Open education of the customers (especially the new online customers) of the banks on how to identify and deal with malicious websites
<i>Element</i>	<i>Treatment</i>
Risk no	4
Incident	Increase in social engineering hacks
Asset	Bank account of the customer or credentials of an employee of a bank
Threat source	Cyber-criminal
Threat	Gathering of personal login information to get authentication information
Attack point	Customer/firm email or phone
Vulnerability	Inadequate knowledge about the existence of social engineering hacks and how to react
Treatment / control	Open education of the customers and employees of the banks on how to identify and deal with these social engineering hackers Incorporating multiple authentication methods, multi factor authentication (Wang et al 2020)

<i>Element</i>	<i>Treatment</i>
Risk no	5
Incident	Data transmission between own device and the bank servers is compromised
Asset	Bank data
Threat source	Malware on the device
Threat	Data transmission is intercepted by someone outside the bank
Attack point	Data link between bank server and the own device
Vulnerability	Misuse of VPN or security protocols
Treatment / control	For communication of official matters the IT Equipment provided by the bank should be used.(Ahmahd, 2020)

<i>Element</i>	<i>Treatment</i>
Risk no	6
Incident	Unsecure videoconferencing
Asset	Bank data
Threat source	Cyber-criminal
Threat	Gathering of confidential data by someone outside the banks
Attack point	Unsecure third party applications (Zoom)
Vulnerability	Inadequate knowledge about the existing threat because of the sudden change in operations. Third party application not being up to the security standards of the bank.
Treatment / control	Open education of the employees on how to use third party apps as secure as possible